

THE CHARACTERIZATION OF AG-80 EPOXY RESIN

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The characterization of epoxy resin is very important for quality control of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin composites. Tetraglycidyl-4,4'-diaminodiphenyl methane (TGDDM) resin, the commercial name of which is AG-80, is a new kind of widely used resin in matrix of composites. This thesis presents the characterization results on the constitute and the batch to batch difference of AG-80 epoxy resin by means of high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), infrared spectroscopy (IR), ^1H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) etc.

The HPLC curves of four batches AG-80 resin solved in the acetonitrile are shown in Fig.1 to Fig.4.

Fig.1 The HPLC curve of sample 0#

Fig.2 The HPLC curve of sample 2#

Fig.3 The HPLC curve of sample 3#

Fig.4 The HPLC curve of sample 5#

The polarity of individual peak decreases with the increase of the retent time. In order of polarity, the components in AG-80 can be divided into five groups: unreacted material, the partial reacted material and hydrolyzate of monomer, the TGDDM monomer, the dimer and its corresponding oligomer, the trimer and the oligomers with higher polymerization degree than three. The content of each group is listed in table 1. There are obvious differences from batch to batch in the composition. The results get from IR of these four batches show in table 2. In sample 0# and 3#, the amount of hydroxyl or ether linkage is higher but the amount of epoxide group less. There are more epoxide groups in sample 5# and less hydroxyls in sample 2#.

Table 1 The component of four batches of AG-80

group No.	0#	2#	3#	5#
1	0.18±0.22	0.14±0.08	0.22±0.22	0.33±0.23
2	4.93±0.14	3.18±0.11	6.93±0.34	4.32±0.28
3	71.94±0.90	88.76±0.11	65.83±1.53	83.0 ±1.90
4	5.22±0.30	4.65±0.35	6.34±0.43	11.55±0.78
5	17.5	1.41	20	0.27

Table 2 The relative content of functional group

sample No.	hydroxyl	ether linkage		epoxide group
	$\frac{A_{3450}}{A_{1505}}$	$\frac{A_{1120}}{A_{1190}}$	$\frac{A_{1072}}{A_{1190}}$	$\frac{A_{906}}{A_{1505}}$
0#	0.52±0.008	0.444±0.040	0.258±0.010	0.227±0.030
2#	0.041±0.011	0.348±0.082	0.225±0.009	0.241±0.042
3#	0.068±0.009	0.441±0.041	0.253±0.007	0.239±0.021
5#	0.043±0.009	0.253±0.011	0.148±0.007	0.302±0.036

and 3#, the amount of hydroxyl or ether linkage is higher but the amount of epoxide group less. There are more epoxide groups in sample 5# and less hydroxyls in sample 2#.

As the result of ^1H NMR experiment, it is found that there are difference between batches in the integrated area ratio of peak in $\delta = 3.03$ ppm caused by the resonance of the two protons on $\gamma\text{N-CH}_2-$ to the area of peak in $\delta = 7.05$ ppm caused by the protons on phenyl, see Table 3

Table 3 The relative content of $\gamma\text{N-CH}_2-$ structure

	0#	2#	3#	5#
$\frac{\delta 3.03}{\delta 7.05}$	2.099	0.944	3.25	0.768

IR and ^1H NMR results confirm the analysis from HPLC, i.e. the sample 3#, 0# and 2# contain more oligomers with polymerization degree higher than three, while the sample 5# contains more dimer. All these four batches contain certain amount of partial reactive substances and hydrolyzate of monomer besides the ideal monomer. All the differences between the batches will affect the processibility such as viscosity (Fig.5) and average molecule number (Table 4), reactivity (Fig.6) and mechanical properties (Table 5).

Table 4 The average molecule number of the batches

	0#	2#	3#	5#
\bar{M}_n	972	491	1089	530

Table 5 The mechanical property of casting resin

sample	σ_f (MPa)	E_f ($\times 10^3$ MPa)	ρ (g/cm 3)
5#	118.6±20.03	4.55±0.44	1.25±0.005
3#	65.56±19.88	4.01±0.45	1.21±0.021
2#	84.84±18.74	3.95±0.31	1.23±0.007

Fig.5 The viscosity of AG-80 under natural cooling condition

Fig. 6 The DSC of AG-80/DDS/BF₃:MEA system

As the result of the chasacterazation above, the following conclusions can be made.

*AG-80 epoxy resin contains several kinds of by-product and oligomers as well as ideal monomer, the resin which contains higher ideal monomer and a certain amount of dimer and without the oligomer with the polymerization degree more than three will be considered good in quality.

* The quantitative difference in composition between different batched of AG-80 resin do exists, which affects its properties during application, so the characterization of AG-80 by HPLC is necessary for guaranteeing the quality stability of composites.